

Protocol for Batch Cropping Images in ImageJ/Fiji

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Download ImageJ (Fiji)

Download ImageJ (Fiji) for free here: <https://imagej.net/software/fiji/>

Option 1. Batch Crop as an Image Sequence:

*NOTE: This approach of batch cropping an image sequence does not work well if images are not exactly at the same scale and/or the region of interest (ROI) is not in the same location in every image. Consequently, “**Option 2**” (below), using a macro that allows the user to select the region of interest in each image, is a better choice for ensuring accurate cropping, but is ultimately a slower process (100 images = ~10 minutes).

1. Open ImageJ; go to Edit > Options > Memory & Threads.. > type in “12000” MB or higher depending on your system capacity; hit OK and close / re-open ImageJ. (6000images = 49000MB)
 - a. at most, the memory you allocate to ImageJ should be at least 1000 MB less than your computer’s total RAM
 - b. You can confirm how much memory is actually available when running ImageJ by clicking on the status bar. You will see a “[used] of [max]” memory message.

2. Go to Import > Image sequence... > “Folder containing your images”; select the first JPEG in the folder only, hit OK if sequence options are correct to import your images. (e.g. for 754 images, total 74 MB, the import is ~110 sec.)
3. In the first image, use Rectangle selection tool to select an area around the berries. Use Image > Crop (Ctrl Shift X)
4. If desired, use Analyze > Set Scale and set global to known px/mm for your images. (*not relevant in this instance as these images of berries appear to be taken at different scales considering the plate as a reference)
5. Save your edited images (File > Save as > Image sequence... > JPEG, etc. > “Cropped Images”)
6. Close ImageJ; do NOT save changes to your original images.

Option 2. Batch Crop using a Macro:

This macro requires the user to specify the region of interest (ROI) to be cropped in each image. The macro will 1) load an image from a user-specified directory in ImageJ, 2) prompt the user to select a region in the image to be cropped with the rectangle tool, 3) crop the image to that user-specified area of interest, 4) save the cropped image to the directory, 5) open the next image in the directory. This process will continue until the last image in the folder has been cropped.

Cropping macro available for download here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5559119>

1. Copy all the images you wish to crop in a single folder. NOTE: This macro will save the cropped image over the original image in that folder! If you would like to keep a set of the original images, have them saved in another location as well.
2. Open ImageJ; go to Plugins > Macros > Run > navigate to and select location of macro (*Crop images.ijm*) on computer and select “Open”
3. Navigate to the location of your folder containing the images you wish to crop and select “Open”
4. Macro will immediately open the first image in the folder and cue up the “Rectangle” selection tool to select an area to be cropped
5. Once you have the rectangle positioned around your region of interest, click “OK”. The macro will automatically crop and save your image to the same folder as a .jpg, then bring up the next image.
6. Repeat the process until you have gone through all images in the folder (estimated time: 100 images = ~10 minutes)